

Source: Sadjadi S, [Heravi MM](#). Pd@tetrahedral hollow magnetic nanoparticles coated with N-doped porous carbon as an efficient catalyst for hydrogenation of nitroarenes. *Appl Organomet Chem.* 2019;33(11). <https://doi.org/10.1002/aoc.5229>

Pd@tetrahedral hollow magnetic nanoparticles coated with N-doped porous carbon as an efficient catalyst for hydrogenation of nitroarenes

Samahe Sadjadi¹, [Majid M. Heravi](#)²

1- Gas Conversion Department, Faculty of Petrochemicals, Iran Polymer and Petrochemicals Institute, 15km Tehran-Karaj Highway, Pajuhesh Science and Technology Park, Pajuhesh Boulevard PO Box 14975-112, Tehran, Iran

2- Department of Chemistry, School of Science, Alzahra University, PO Box 1993891176, Vanak, Tehran, Iran

Abstract

Hollow magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs) with tetrahedral morphology were synthesized and then covered by a shell prepared by coating with melamine–formaldehyde followed by the introduction of glucose-derived carbon. Subsequently, Pd nanoparticles were immobilized and the core–shell nanocomposite was carbonized. The obtained magnetic catalyst was successfully applied for the hydrogenation of nitroarenes in aqueous media. To investigate the effects of the morphology of MNPs, the nature of carbon shell, and the order of incorporation of Pd nanoparticles, several control catalysts, including the MNPs with different morphologies (disc-like and cylinder); MNPs coated with different shells (sole glucose-derived carbon or melamine–formaldehyde carbon shell); and a nanocomposite, in which Pd was immobilized after carbonization, were prepared and examined as catalyst for the model reaction. To justify the observed different catalytic activities of the catalysts, their Pd loadings, leaching, and specific surface areas were compared. The results confirmed that tetrahedral MNPs coated with porous N-rich carbon

Source: Sadjadi S, [Heravi MM](https://doi.org/10.1002/aoc.5229). Pd@tetrahedral hollow magnetic nanoparticles coated with N-doped porous carbon as an efficient catalyst for hydrogenation of nitroarenes. *Appl Organomet Chem.* 2019;33(11). <https://doi.org/10.1002/aoc.5229>

shell exhibited the best catalytic activity. The high catalytic activity of this catalyst was attributed to its high surface area and the interaction of N-rich shell with Pd nanoparticles that led to the higher Pd loading and suppressed Pd leaching.

Keywords: catalyst, hydrogenation, magnetic nanoparticles, N-doped carbon